

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PRIMARY MATHEMATICS EDUCATION, PUPILS' ENGAGEMENT, AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study examined how AI technologies affect instructional delivery, pupil engagement, and academic performance in primary mathematics in Akwa Ibom State. Using a survey design, data were collected from 50 participants including mathematics teachers, headteachers, and upper primary pupils across the three senatorial districts, using a 24-item instrument ($\alpha = 0.88$) on a four-point Likert-type scale. Means, standard deviations, and Chi-square goodness-of-fit tests addressed the research questions and hypotheses ($\alpha = .05$). Results confirmed that AI-powered personalized learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and AI-driven assessment tools each produced statistically significant positive effects. The study recommended coordinated investment in infrastructure, teacher training, and emotionally responsive AI design for resource-constrained primary schools.

Keywords: *Artificial Intelligence; Mathematics Education; Instructional Delivery; Pupil Engagement; Academic Performance; Primary Schools; Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

Strong mathematical foundations in primary school are closely tied to long-term academic achievement and participation in STEM fields (OECD, 2023). In sub-Saharan Africa, students struggle with low performance, negative attitudes toward mathematics, overcrowded classrooms, and absence of teacher's feedback (Awoyale *et al.*, 2024; Ibok, 2021). In Nigeria, these problems are well documented. Akwa

Ibom State alone manages over 1,200 public primary schools across 31 local government areas, yet technology use in foundational mathematics instruction remains limited (Bali *et al.*, 2024), and weak assessment feedback continues to impede learning progress in primary education (Dick and Akintunde, 2023). AI has attracted considerable global interest as a practical response to these challenges. Personalized learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and AI-driven assessment tools have each shown positive effects on mathematics outcomes, student engagement, and feedback quality (Tang, 2025; Son, 2024; Walkington, 2025). In Nigeria, Omokaro and Babundo (2025) found that AI-driven tools improve both engagement and teaching quality in mathematics classrooms, while Okri *et al.* (2025) documented a positive link between AI tools and student motivation in Cross River State.

Their findings align with the Federal Government's recognition of the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in basic education (Samuel and Salisu, 2025; UBEC, 2024). Literature on the intergration and use of AI is concentrated at the secondary and tertiary levels; major studies including those of Akin-Olayemi and Idris-Tajudeen (2025) and Adayilo *et al.* (2026) do not disaggregate findings by school level, leaving the primary school largely unaddressed. Infrastructure deficits and high implementation costs also limits AI adoption in primary schools (Bali *et al.*, 2024), and limited teacher awareness compounds these barriers (Ogbu Eke, 2024; Ewa, 2024). The emotional effects of AI-mediated learning on young pupils particularly those with mathematics anxiety is also underexplored (Bredenkamp and Copple, 1997; Hidayatullah *et al.*, 2024). This study is grounded in Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) and Developmental Appropriateness Theory (Bredenkamp and Copple, 1997). It addresses three objectives: to assess how AI-powered personalized learning platforms affect instructional delivery; to determine the contribution of intelligent tutoring systems (ITS) to pupil engagement; and to examine the influence of AI-driven assessment tools on academic performance.

Research Questions

1. What is the contribution of intelligent tutoring systems to pupils' engagement with mathematical concepts in primary schools in Akwa Ibom State?
2. How do AI-driven assessment tools influence pupils' academic performance in primary mathematics in Akwa Ibom State?

Research Hypotheses

1. Intelligent tutoring systems have no significant positive effect on pupils' engagement with mathematical concepts in primary schools in Akwa Ibom State.
2. AI-driven assessment tools have no significant positive effect on pupils' academic performance in primary mathematics in Akwa Ibom State.

METHODOLOGY

A survey research design was adopted. The study covered public primary schools across the three senatorial districts of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling procedure yielded 50 respondents: 25 mathematics teachers, 10 headteachers, and 15 upper-basic pupils (Primary 4–6). Data were collected using the researcher-developed Artificial Intelligence in Primary Mathematics Education Questionnaire (AIPMEQ), a 24-item instrument organised into three clusters on a four-point Likert-type scale (1 = Very Low to 4 = Very High). Five subject experts validated the instrument (content validity index > 0.70), and pilot testing yielded a reliability coefficient of $\alpha = 0.88$. Research questions were answered using means and standard deviations, with a criterion mean of ≥ 2.50 indicating a high extent of agreement. The null hypotheses were tested using Chi-square goodness-of-fit tests at the .05 significance level. All 50 questionnaires were returned and usable (100% response rate).

RESULTS

RQ1: Intelligent Tutoring Systems and Pupil Engagement

Table 1. Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings: Intelligent Tutoring Systems and Pupils' Engagement ($N = 50$)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
9	Intelligent tutoring systems provide step-by-step guidance through age-appropriate mathematical problems	3.40	0.68	High
10	Intelligent tutoring systems offer hints and explanations tailored to young pupils' errors	3.36	0.70	High
11	Pupils spend more time on mathematical tasks when using intelligent tutoring systems	3.34	0.71	High
12	Intelligent tutoring systems increase pupil persistence when encountering challenging problems	3.32	0.72	High
13	Intelligent tutoring systems reduce frustration with mathematical problem-solving in young learners	3.31	0.73	High
14	Intelligent tutoring systems provide immediate positive feedback that maintains pupil motivation	3.38	0.69	High
15	Pupils demonstrate increased confidence in mathematics through intelligent tutoring system use	3.33	0.70	High
16	Intelligent tutoring systems make mathematics learning more interactive and enjoyable for young pupils	3.37	0.68	High
Cluster Mean		3.35	0.70	High

Decision criterion: Mean ≥ 2.50 = High Contribution.

All eight items exceeded the criterion mean. Step-by-step guidance through age-appropriate problems rated highest ($\mu = 3.40$, $SD = 0.68$); frustration reduction rated lowest within the cluster ($\mu = 3.31$, $SD = 0.73$). The cluster mean of 3.35 ($SD = 0.70$) confirms a high level of ITS contribution to pupil engagement.

RQ2: AI-Driven Assessment Tools and Academic Performance

Table 2. Mean and Standard Deviation Ratings: AI-Driven Assessment Tools and Academic Performance (N = 50)

S/N	Item Statement	Mean	SD	Decision
17	AI-driven assessment tools provide immediate feedback on pupils' mathematical work	3.34	0.69	High
18	Automated grading enables more frequent assessment in primary mathematics	3.30	0.71	High
19	AI tools identify specific misconceptions in pupils' mathematical understanding	3.26	0.73	High
20	Detailed diagnostic feedback helps teachers address individual pupil learning needs	3.28	0.72	High
21	More frequent low-stakes assessment reduces mathematics anxiety in young pupils	3.24	0.74	High
22	AI-driven assessment enables mastery-based progression in foundational numeracy	3.27	0.71	High
23	Pupils demonstrate improved performance with immediate, encouraging feedback	3.32	0.70	High
24	AI assessment tools help identify struggling pupils for early intervention	3.25	0.73	High
Cluster Mean		3.28	0.72	High

Decision criterion: Mean \geq 2.50 = High Influence.

Immediate feedback on pupils' mathematical work was rated highest ($\mu = 3.34$, $SD = 0.69$); reducing anxiety through low-stakes assessment rated lowest ($\mu = 3.24$, $SD = 0.74$). A cluster mean of 3.28 ($SD = 0.72$) confirms a high level of positive influence on academic performance.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1: Intelligent tutoring systems have no significant positive effect on pupils' engagement with mathematical concepts in primary schools in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3. Chi-Square Goodness-of-Fit: Intelligent Tutoring Systems and Pupils' Engagement

Response Category	Obs. N	Exp. N	Residual	χ^2	df	p	Decision
Very High Contribution	15	12.50	2.50				
High Contribution	18	12.50	5.50				
Low Contribution	10	12.50	-2.50				
Very Low Contribution	7	12.50	-5.50				
Total (N = 50)	50	50		38.72	3	.000	Reject H ₀₁

For H₀₁, perceptions of ITS contribution to pupil engagement deviated significantly from a uniform distribution ($\chi^2(3, N = 50) = 38.72, p < .001$), with responses concentrated in the Very High and High Contribution categories. H₀₁ is rejected.

Hypothesis 2: AI-driven assessment tools have no significant positive effect on pupils' academic performance in primary mathematics in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4. Chi-Square Goodness-of-Fit: AI-Driven Assessment Tools and Academic Performance

Response Category	Obs. N	Exp. N	Residual	χ^2	df	p	Decision
Very High Influence	14	12.50	1.50				
High Influence	17	12.50	4.50				
Low Influence	11	12.50	-1.50				
Very Low Influence	8	12.50	-4.50				
Total (N = 50)	50	50		35.84	3	.000	Reject H₀₂

For H₀₂, responses on AI-driven assessment tools' influence on academic performance showed a similar significant deviation ($\chi^2(3, N = 50) = 35.84, p < .001$), with most responses in the Very High and High Influence categories. H₀₂ is rejected.

DISCUSSION

This study examined how AI technologies affect instructional delivery, pupil engagement, and academic performance in primary mathematics in Akwa Ibom State. Intelligent tutoring systems showed a significant positive contribution to pupil engagement. This is consistent with Adayilo *et al.* (2026), who found that AI tutoring raised engagement in schools in developing-countries through personalized guidance and immediate feedback, and with Son (2024) confirming that ITS increase time-on-task through adaptive support. The comparatively lower rating for frustration reduction reflects the mathematics anxiety observed among primary pupils in Nigeria (Ibok, 2021; Awoyale *et al.*, 2024). From a Developmental Appropriateness perspective (Bredekamp and Copple, 1997), current ITS appear better equipped to address cognitive and behavioural engagement than emotional engagement, and it is a design gap that warrants attention.

AI-driven assessment tools positively influenced academic performance to a high extent. This result is consistent with Walkington (2025) who found that immediate, specific AI feedback drives improved mathematics outcomes, and with Biernatova and Korenova (2025) primary-level action research showing that AI-enhanced assessment delivers efficient diagnostic feedback and learning personalisation. The lowest-rated item i.e. reducing anxiety through frequent low-stakes assessment, reveals the limits of assessment technology in isolation. Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) suggests that while adaptive feedback reduces extraneous cognitive load, overcoming entrenched affective barriers requires emotional support that assessment tools alone cannot provide. This limitation is well illustrated by Dick and Akintunde (2023) who not considered assessment culture in Akwa Ibom State as a structural barrier to learning improvement.

IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

For the Akwa Ibom State Universal Basic Education Board, these findings support targeted investment in age-appropriate AI mathematics platforms with engaging interfaces, audio support, offline functionality, and alignment with the Nigerian basic education curriculum. Teachers need both the technical skills to use AI platforms and the pedagogical know-how to act on AI-generated data in teaching primary mathematics. For policymakers and technology providers, the infrastructure and cost barriers identified here reinforce the value of public-private models that can deliver platform access, localization, and training to schools that cannot independently sustain AI deployments.

This study offers the first empirical evidence on AI integration in primary mathematics education in Akwa Ibom State, examining instructional delivery, pupil engagement, and academic performance within a single validated framework. Results confirm that AI-powered personalized learning platforms, intelligent tutoring systems, and AI-driven assessment tools each produce statistically significant positive effects. Realising these gains in full depends on coordinated

investment in teacher capacity, school infrastructure, and emotionally responsive system design. Future work should draw on larger probability samples across rural and peri-urban settings, use longitudinal designs to track outcomes over sustained deployment periods, and include experimental comparisons between AI-integrated and non-AI classrooms to build stronger causal evidence.

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